

Appendix: stages of development from the era of archaic humans to the axial age

The oldest known skeleton of an anatomically modern *Homo sapiens* dates to about 200,000 years ago. It is widely agreed in archaeological and anthropological literature that the emergence of language and transition to “modern” behaviour occurred some 40,000-50,000 years ago. It seems that a few preliminary changes preceded this transition some 70,000-50,000 years ago, at the time when humans started to move out of Africa (e.g. Klein, 1995; Lewis-Williams, 2004, chp 3; for a more sceptical view partly based on methodological problems, see Henshilwood & Marean, 2003). What the widely agreed view implies that for the first 150,000 years of its existence, nothing distinguished *Homo sapiens* from the more archaic species of humans, with which it much later interbred in various parts of Eurasia.

Many sources suggest that during the transition some 40,000-50,000 years ago, a “fully modern” behaviour, consciousness, mind, and/or language would have emerged quite abruptly. What “abrupt” means in this context is rarely discussed. In social sciences, a *longue durée* of history – the longest conceivable period of continuity at some level of social reality – is supposed to take from a few hundred up to a thousand years (see Braudel, 1980). How “abrupt” can a process of change be that lasts a few thousands of years if not more? In itself, this question is suggestive of the acceleration of processes of change over time, requiring explanation. In any case, Table 1 summarises the idea that there was a sudden change after a long period of continuity that lasted, in essence, for about two million years counting from the beginning of the era of *homo erectus*. This view is usually associated with the idea that some kind of genetic or neural change must have caused the transition, though it would be difficult to explain how a genetic change could have occurred so rapidly across the world. The more plausible explanation focusses on the capacity of the brain to restructure itself on the basis of experiences and communications and in terms of its networks of neurons and synapses. The neuronal-synoptic change may result from this autopoietic (self-producing and self-creative) capacity, which, after a certain turning point, is capable of enabling lasting forms of emergence also in the absence of any significant (epi) genetic change.

In the simple model of Table 1, the transition is assumed to have occurred between two types of consciousness, “primary” and “higher-order”. Primary consciousness is present-centric and involves no language. The idea is that after the transition, humans suddenly have the capacity for “full” or “fully modern” temporality, understanding of “we”, conception of self, and modern language (whatever that may mean), as they are by now living in large and complex societies where social distinctions and also conflicts occur. Since then, humans would have remained the same, implying that there is no essential difference between a shaman from 30,000 BCE and John Searle or Tony Lawson.

Table 1: A simple dichotomist view of two forms of consciousness

Primary consciousness	Present-centric	No concept of a personal self	No capacity to view images from the vantage point of social self	No language	No social distinctions	Size and complexity: primary bands of c. 30 individuals
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Higher order consciousness	Capacity to see the past and the future	A conception of self	Recognition of his or her acts or affections from the point of view of the collective self	Fully modern language	Social distinctions, diversity, discrimination, conflicts	Size and complexity: organized settlement patterns and extensive “trade” in specialised items → a loosely organised network of primary bands, with the core bands spending a part of the year together
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Sources: Summarised from Edelman 1992, 113–32; Lewis-Williams 2004, 69–100

From a scientific or critical realist perspective, emergence means that elements are combined and organised in a novel way, resulting in new qualities and causal powers. The process of emergence takes time. In the process, the pre-existing elements may assume new functions. Hence the causes of their development can be different from the causes of their reproduction and development in a new context. Although it is true that evolution and history sometimes exhibit discontinuities or “jumps”, it seems more plausible to suggest that the linguistic form emerged from interactions between multiple processes and through different mechanisms at several different time frames from phylogenetic and epigenetic to developmental, historical (*longue durée* and shorter durations), and interactional. Changes in linguistic abilities must arise in parallel with advances in cognitive or social abilities. (Cangelosi, 2005, 187; MacWhinney, 2005, 194). The gradual emergence of culture and society from nature may have involved periods of rapid change, but in general the process was at first very slow and accelerated through time as cultural and social processes and mechanisms became more central (like all layers of reality, culture remains dependent on earlier and lower layers). What is important from an epistemic viewpoint is that the resulting new qualities and causal powers are observable in the archaeological record.

The starting point of Table 2 is that the emergence of language, consciousness and complex society has been a long process with multiple phases. Its end-point, however conceived and located, is not “fully modern”, but rather something that remains subject to further open-ended developments. From this perspective, the apparent discontinuity of Table 1 would seem to require an almost miraculous neural (or genetic) change in the anatomically modern *homo sapiens*, in spite of the complexity of numerous anatomical, cognitive, social and ecological elements that played a role in the slow and multi-phased emergence of language and reflective consciousness. Here I can only give a literature-based and indicative account of some of the developments that were involved in this long and complicated process (the summary of Table 2 accords also with the basic thrust of Tomasello’s [2008] well-known constructivist theory of language development). A vast variety of distinct complexity-increasing mechanisms and systems (cf. Clayton, 2013) contributed to the gradual adaptation of human systems in ecological contexts. It is worth stressing that only hominins started to adapt by means of developing social intelligence and cooperative skills and by increasing group size. This was only an evolutionary option among many, as for instance the line leading to the current chimpanzee illustrates.

The point of Table 2 is to illuminate the steps required before a Searlean or CR social ontology may be even remotely adequate. The table depicts seven stages of development. It is based on the idea that cognitive and communicative capabilities, size of relevant groups and metagroups, population density and ecological conditions are intra- and interrelated in multiple ways, including in terms of opposing causal tendencies. A given narrow ecological niche in an area can sustain only a very small number of people. A shift to larger size is thus difficult. To increase the size, new qualities and powers must evolve, but they in turn would already presuppose larger communities. A problem is that in primates, social

Table 2: Seven stages from primary consciousness to the ancient world

1. Primary consciousness	Communication through variety of signals mostly genetically determined (some intentionality)	No capacity to view images from the vantage point of social self	No concept of personal self, but ability of self-identification in front of a mirror	Present-centric	Tools are invented and used ad hoc, not transmitted culturally	Social structure established at present & is dominated by strong males and their sexual drive	Size and complexity: primary bands of c. 15-30 individuals
2. Culture based on imitation	Communication through variety of complex signals that are increasingly intentional	Sociability, inherent capacity to understand others' intentions and imitate	No concept of personal self, but as above & self-initiated and representational acts that are intentional, though not linguistic	Implied future-orientation (danger, design of artefacts etc)	Stone-made tools, but little if any developments in the scale of 10 ⁵ years	Egalitarian sharing; social differentiation unclear; probably some sexual division of labour	Size and complexity: primary bands of c. 15-30 individuals, size perhaps slowly increasing, with (quasi-) regular interactions with other similar bands
3. First elements of spoken language: intentional calls, modifiers and commands	Commands emerging from intentional calls and modifiers (e.g. "sharper"!)	Responsiveness to others and their intentions (tacit recognition of the social self)	No concept of personal self, but as above & intentional acts partly linguistic	Implied future-orientation (danger, design etc), with wider action-possibilities	New types of tools that require more concentration and learning; increasing diversity of materials	Minor social differentiation, involving also tacit claims to knowledge (shamans, teachers)	Size and complexity: the density of population increases and the wider networks start to become more organised
4. Nouns & some rules of language-use	Once modifiers and commands stabilised, nouns for life/animals and first rudimentary sentences evolve; gradually also nouns for things	The social self occurs though hallucinated images and commands that drive activities from tool-making to cave-paintings	No concept of personal self, but as above & ritual burials suggest that some individuals are already assuming special significance	Images & enduring complex tasks → non-present becomes real, also through dreams and hallucinations (other-worldly) → cave-paintings	Further diversification of tools and the emergence of drawing of animals; and then invention of pottery, pendants, ornaments, barbed harpoons and spearheads	The emergence of social distinctions, diversity, discrimination & conflicts in what still remains partly egalitarian and non-differentiated context	Size and complexity: tribal metagroups, establishing a wider "we" of togetherness (acting together, coordinating activities also across seasons etc) → further stabilisation of language
5. Names & context-sensitive and partly still unstable syntax and other rules of language-use	With larger & fixed populations & social differentiation, individuals start to be identified by names; full sentences; syntactical language with subject-object-verb structure	Hallucinated images and voices can be named → social self assumes new forms of existence, and it is in this context that not only named gods but also, strict coordination problems start to emerge	The concept of personal self evolving, e.g. ceremonial graves become a common practice → individuals are recognised as personal and can be remembered also after their deaths	As in stage 2, but other-worldliness becomes more clearly articulated; hallucinations assume greater role in individual behaviour	Language allows for greater individuation of things, bringing about more sophisticated and diverse artefacts & accumulation of cultural knowledge about plants and animals	Social differentiation increases and becomes more established involving conflicts, which are difficult to resolve without a strict hierarchy based on the authority of gods	Settlements become more permanent and metagroups larger; rudimentary experimentation with agriculture; over time the first towns of a few hundred people evolve & around them larger area and networks; these developments result in chiefdoms

6. “Bicameral mind”: symbolic language, book-keeping and eventually writing, mathematics and justice; writing: proceeding from pictures of visual events to symbols of phonetic events; syntax and other rules consolidated	Syntax & rules become more stable as language-use becomes ritualised in a larger community and as new words, concepts and expressions evolve	Hierarchy emerges as a solution to the coordination problem: a powerful god, voice of god through king and large temple & an organised religion with specialised roles, tied with a system of production and distribution, is the social self.	The dead and especially dead kings speak long after death; but also their replacements, god-statues etc appear to speak and demand sacrifices; the collective whole (= god) assesses individuals identified with names, e.g. in terms of justice	Long-term projects (future) and long-distance exchange (spatial outside) become possible; sacrifices for the god; afterlife (burials with food, tools and weapons provided for the dead etc)	Further individuation of things, bringing about more sophisticated and diverse artefacts & accumulation of cultural knowledge about plants and animals, resulting in domesticated animals and collectively organised agriculture	Social differentiation and steep hierarchy deepens; division of labour involves specialised roles transmitted culturally, including specialisation in violence; religious hierarchy may not be sufficient to resolve conflicts → possibility of (civil) war	Early civilizations become larger, collectively organised agriculture & central towns grow into small cities up to 10 ⁴ inhabitants; practical reason and techniques become more sophisticated, but gods/god-kings decide; individuals may nonetheless follow their own “voices” and desires → conflicts → laws
7. Reflective consciousness and agency: emergence of metaphorical mind-space, the analogy “I”, the metaphor “me”, narratisation, compatibilisation etc.; written language can fix meanings and rules across contexts	Oral stories written down and copied in a canonised form; documents and letters become more commonplace; the beginning of philosophy, science, and arts; further expansion of words, concepts and expressions	Collective self evolves in interaction with personal self; possibility of reasoned dialogue; hierarchies, justice, truth and also gods are questioned; this questioning remains rare and is conditioned by older layers and scales of efficient communication	People not only have a personal self but can also systematically cultivate it; gods become increasingly silent; what they or god-like teachers once spoke, can be written down and the text treated as holy; for some gods are only objects of human belief	Utopian thinking and linear time evolve & soon questioned and debated; long-term projects and designs still focus largely on afterlife and gods, apart from military issues; other-worldliness is nonetheless no longer self-evident	New (for us ancient) art, artefacts and technology in the hubs of the Old World; capacity for long-distance sea-travel and navigation; horses make land-communication and travel faster; dominant forms in the hubs: city-states and military-agrarian empires	New institutions such as money make abstract systems of exchange and domination possible; development of professional bureaucracy, written law and systems of education; large empires are led by those specialising in violence	City-states (“freedom from tyrants”) are vulnerable to attacks by military-agrarian empires or may evolve into an empire; the vastest empires 50-100 x 10 ⁶ people; voice-hearing suppressed; slavery is common, but also independent farming and industry; system-integration across vast spaces may fail → (civil) war

complexity increases rapidly with group size, and social complexity requires enhanced cognitive powers and larger brains (Donald, 1991, 137). The transition from stage 1 to stage 2 was occurring through (epi) genetic changes and was very slow. Also the transition from stage 2 to stage 3 took at least 1.5 million years. It was only after the emergence of culture that the process started to accelerate.

Also non-human primates can have a primary consciousness. For example, chimpanzees imitate behaviour (Hill, Barton & Hurtado, 2009, 190) and can learn to use a set of words if taught, but they lack the ability to realize the intentions of others. At the stage of primary consciousness, tools can be used on an ad hoc basis, but not transmitted culturally. “The [...] lives [of those with primary consciousness] are lived entirely in the present, as a series of concrete episodes, and the highest element in their system of memory representation seems to be at the level of event representation” (Donald, 1991, 149). The transition from state 1 to stage 2 does not yet distinguish humans from other primates in any categorical

fashion, though becoming increasingly cultural is unique (by cultural I mean transmission of skills and knowledge by means of learning rather than biologically). Culture does not imply spoken language, but requires some intentional communications that can be sustained by a combination of gestures, body language, imitation and sounds. This stage lasted relatively long, especially if compared to later historical times.

It is possible that first elements of spoken language such as intentional calls, modifiers and commands (Jaynes, 2000, 131-3) emerged in some form in archaic hominins, but *homo sapiens* – in its evolving diversity – turned out to have unprecedented potential in this regard. Based on archaeological records, it seems likely that this phase coincided with the human movement from Africa to Eurasia. Adaptation to new circumstances and encounters with more archaic humans (involving interbreeding with them) seems to have accelerated the development toward stage 4. New qualities and powers emerged. Larger groups are crucial for the stability of expressions and their meaning, while they were also made possible by the development of the early forms of language. Some human communities seem to have reached this stage about 40,000-50,000 years ago. With concepts (of animals in particular) and some shared rules of language-use, new qualities and causal powers both at the level of human brain and social community emerged. The new powers left some crucial traces for us to observe (stage 4). Language enables concentration on tasks that require time, while at this point also dreams, hallucinations, and powerful images were experienced as real (for first-hand evidence of collective hallucination by contemporary hunter-gatherers, see Everett, 2008, xv-xvii, 137). These images were replicated for instance in shamanistic cave-paintings, probably for communal purposes and as an indication of access to the other world (cf. the slightly different accounts of Jaynes, 2000, 134–45; Lewis-Williams, 2002, 101–35). As ornaments – possibly carved in tools – images could serve as identity-markers as well. Conditions changed bit by bit during the latest phases of the last Ice Age. Some of the megafauna became locally or totally extinct, in part probably because of human activities. With increased capacity for tool- and clothes-making and cooperation, the new possibilities for adaptation led to slow population growth – enough to prove detrimental to the remaining archaic humans (for example the Neanderthals disappeared from Europe some 40,000 and 37,000 years ago, and in other places soon after).

At stage 5, individuals acquire names while language-rules, including syntax, become more complex and stable (even if they at this stage remain volatile and excessively context-sensitive). Language is made possible by the human capacity to imitate and recognise the intention of others, but once established at some level, it became something that is experienced in part as an external reality. Approaching this stage, humans confuse the individual and group, thus lack a differentiated subjectivity; do not have any mental or metaphorical vocabulary; may lack also concepts for instance for colours and numbers; cannot narratize and thus have no history; are not concerned about the future but rather live through each day as it comes; and do not have gods or religion (cf. Everett, 2008). However, religion emerges in the course of stage 5. Both individual humans and dreamed and hallucinated voices and images start to acquire names, though for a long while these names may change from time to time (an individual may be renamed several times in relation to collective categories based on for example on age). There is little if any differentiation between non-living and living nature and the human cultural world. Later, especially when agriculture-based chiefdoms with wider division of labour evolve, particular spirits of nature and various gods might also provide “explanations” as to why things happen (cf. Wright, 2009, 9–69).

At stage 5, some settlements are becoming more permanent (at least for a part of the year) and metagroups larger. Eventually a few metagroups start to experiment with agriculture. The development of language greatly facilitates this experimentation: new names to things increases

perception and attention and can lead to accumulation of knowledge (Jaynes, 2000, 138). Domestication (acculturation) of some animals was the first step. Agrovillages form a new energy-system: “the sunlight was converted into food energy by the green fields of crops now ‘inside’ the cultural system” (Volk, 2017, 135). Agriculture may not have been an obvious choice or a conscious choice at all (Diamond, 1997, 104–13), but some of those communities, which started to pursue this path, eventually expanded – the first of them about 30,000 years after the extinction of Neanderthals. In this process, social differentiation increases and becomes more established. With language/brain experienced as “speaking” to oneself directly – and often giving commands – conflicts become increasingly difficult to resolve without a hierarchy. Through a social-evolutionary process, this development resulted invariably in chiefdoms, common in all parts of the world. Those at the top of the religious hierarchy claim privileged access to the world of gods (as already shamans did in some but more limited ways). This ensures social harmony and enables planning, while it also establishes separate classes of people, and involves the possibility of exploitation and discrimination.

Stage 6 corresponds to what Jaynes (2000; see also Kujsten, 2006) calls “bicameral mind”. What is noteworthy about both stages 5 and 6 is that volition, planning, and initiative are organized with no reflective consciousness or reflexivity. Jaynes (2000, 117–25) maintains that one side of the brain was in essence giving instructions and commands to the other side. Over time this phenomenon became increasingly enmeshed with social division of labour and hierarchy. What I think is undeniable is that language drastically shapes human brains in terms of its networks of neurons and synapses, but whether this can and should be seen strictly in terms of the left and right hemisphere of the brain is more uncertain (but cf. McGilchrist, 2012). Moreover, while the world of the early civilisations might have been relatively undifferentiated and partly dreamlike and hallucinatory, it would be an exaggeration to see communication at stages 5 or 6 occurring less between people than brain hemispheres (or something equivalent). Probably human-to-human communications (for Jaynes, the left hemisphere) and dream-like, partly hallucinated communications with spirits and gods (right hemisphere, responsible for guiding and planning) appeared side by side. To reiterate, the latter generated a potential coordination problem that became more severe as the community grew. Whenever social or collective action was required, whose voices and visions was to be taken as decisive? We do not know the details of the process that resulted in the steeply hierarchical systems led by a god-king or by a king hearing god(s). What we do know, however, is that only a few communities followed this path to the stage of early civilizations. Those that did ended up in a system exhibiting striking similarity across the world, whether we are talking about Mesopotamia, Egypt, Indus Valley, and China in the Old World or Incas, Aztecs, and Mayas in the New World. Analogous solutions are found at different levels of reality (Volk, 2017, especially 100–11). Thus the early civilizations can be seen as a cultural version of the society of insects:

Like the queen in a termite nest or a beehive, the idols of a bicameral world are the carefully tended centers of social control, with auditory hallucinations instead of pheromones. (Jaynes, 2000, 144)

Unlike the systems of eusocial animals of bees or ants, however, the early civilizations were cultural and thus liable to rapid changes in terms of skills, division of labour, and means of communication. By this time some people lived in towns of such size that everyone does not know everyone else. Individual social intelligence is partly replaced by more abstract principles of organization, and this leads to the invention of new practices such as book-keeping, which is also the origin of writing. Many features of the early civilizations are difficult to explain without the hypothesis of a bicameral mind (or something equivalent). Why was there at the centre of towns a large building, a house of gods, typically with

a human effigy and a table where people could place their offerings? These buildings were bigger than anything else constructed. Sometimes they were taken as dwellings of gods, which only priests could visit. Why did people offer some of their most precious food, valuable artefacts, and in some cases even their own (or other humans') lives as gifts to dead people or gods? How can all this make sense? The bicameral mind hypothesis suggests that people literally heard dead people and gods talk to them. At times, they could hallucinate seeing them as well. At the heyday of this era, the god-king, priests, and supporting administration (with increasingly specialised skills) organised the functioning of the whole from irrigation and harvests to distribution and construction, all intertwined with religious rituals. The top people had not only a privileged access to gods but also to common resources, marking the beginning of latent class conflict. People living in towns could see the tallest building everywhere, the function of which was to remind them of the powerful god-voice that they needed to obey, even against the voices they heard.

The agricultural city-states were very successful in terms of population growth, notwithstanding unintended consequences and occasional catastrophic outcomes such as salination following centuries of irrigation. Stage 6 did not last very long, only a couple of millennia. Such theocracies with strict hierarchies require stability of setting. Mass-movements of people because of population growth, long-distance trade, changing climate, ecological problems, and wars and invasions meant that people left their stability inducing temples and idols. At the same time, writing relayed the commands of gods in a new way, "weaken[ing] the power of auditory hallucinations" (Jaynes, 2006, 91). Book-keeping and writing stabilised meanings, although at first signs, say 𒌦 (this is an arbitrary example), could stand for several different nouns as well as for several different syllables depending on the context. These ambiguities have made it easy for translators to impose modern categories in order to make translations comprehensible to them. "A translator often reads in more than he reads out" (Jaynes, 2000, 177). Be that as it may, the developments in early civilizations led to increasingly abstract categories. Basic arithmetic followed book-keeping. Soon an abstract concept of value that started to constitute practices of justice and exchange. A case in point is the Mesopotamian shekel that was nominally equivalent to a specific weight of barley. In the Code of Hammurabi (c. 1750), it was used to fix equivalences by divine decree in the context of compensation for wrongdoings and exchange of goods. Soon after this, letters of officials became commonplace and were increasingly used to administer large areas, including through "mythodiplomacy" (Der Derian, 1987, chp 4) with neighbouring city-states that had competing gods and related claims. The hallucinations of shamans/priests/god-kings were gradually replaced by written texts, though for centuries these texts still reflected the contents of the bicameral mind. At around this time some of the early civilizations such as Assyria became increasingly violent. In the absence of auditory hallucinations, cruelty, and oppression become the ways in which a ruler imposes his rule upon his numerous subjects.

Many of the elements of reflective consciousness and early reflexivity evolved gradually during stage 6, including the metaphorical mind-space, the analogy "I", and narratisation. These enabled, among other things, new levels of long-term planning resulting e.g. in walls around cities. The transition to a world of reflectively conscious agency took a few more centuries. Step by step, the increasingly counterproductive voice-hearing was suppressed. The beginning of Karl Jaspers's (1953) axial age dates back to 800 BCE. From the axial age onwards, the most advanced religions revolve around texts that are revealed to humanity through a guru, prophet or a "son of god" that can still hear god, but for the rest of people gods remain mostly silent. Thucydides (c.460 BCE – c.400 BCE) managed to write a story of the Peloponnesian wars where gods played no role except through human beliefs, even though for Thucydides the fall of Athens was also a moral story where it received an almost-cosmic punishment for its ethical decline (Patomäki, 2002). Institutions, such as money, began to take functions that are familiar to people living in a

capitalist market society. City-states continue to operate mostly through oral communication, but they also write constitutions where their key political and judicial institutions are defined. Free men can now condemn tyrannies and praise freedom. Philosophers such as Plato can imagine alternative ways of organising political communities (utopias). However, small city-states are vulnerable to attacks by military-agrarian empires or may evolve into such an empire. The vastest empires (Rome, Han-dynasty China) comprised at their height some 50-100 million people and 5-6 million km². While slavery was common, also independent farming and industry were important. System-integration across vast spaces can easily fail – partly because of unmanageable distances (given also the available means of communication and transportation) and external invasions; partly because the principles of rule were contested (including rules of succession). Various mixes of disintegration and invasions could prompt a civil war, occasionally spelling end to a system of rule, dynasty or an empire as a whole. Some empires were rebuilt many times.

The development through stages is neither linear nor uniform across contexts. Partial regress is possible and communities may stick to their practices even when they interact closely with communities at higher stages. Once several stages are in place, all kinds of combined formations become possible, in which features of a lower stage are merged with those of a later stage of development. Knowledge, skills, artefacts, gods, aspects of language, organising principles and so on can easily diffuse from one place and community to another. Hunter-gatherers may continue with their life-style, at least for a while, even after they have acquired industrially produced goods (clothes, tools etc.) and learnt to speak colonial languages. This makes it especially difficult to identify original stages by observing recent or current practices and systems. Moreover, the combined formations may exhibit contradictions and all kinds of peculiarities. They may deviate so much from the rule and effect such an upheaval as to make the less advanced more powerful for instance in military terms, though later they may adopt elements of the more advanced system (think about the role of Mongols in world history). Some Marxians use the phrase “uneven and combined development” to describe similar phenomena in the contemporary context (Rosenberg, 2016). The idea is generalizable beyond 19th or 20th century capitalism.

The point is that Searlean and critical realist social ontologies presuppose reflective consciousness, reflexivity, and agency (stage 7 or beyond). It is true that in some passages, Searle (1995, e.g. 7) seems to assume that primacy consciousness (stage 1) would suffice for the establishment of institutional facts, but at other times institutional facts are essentially connected to constitutive rules (‘X counts as Y in context C’), self-referential concepts, and performative utterances. Searle (1995, 32) writes for instance that “logically speaking, the statement ‘A certain type of substance, x, is money’ implies an indefinite inclusive disjunction of the form ‘x is used as money or x is regarded as money or x is believed to be money, etc.’”. For money to exist, people (analogy “I”) must have beliefs about other people’s beliefs and practices, which they can relate to themselves (metaphor “me”; cf. Lawson, 2019, chps 5–6). Soon Searle explains further that an institutional fact cannot exist in isolation but only in a wider context. Thus for example money presupposes a system of exchanging goods and services for money. “But in order that it can have a system of exchange, it must have a system of property and property ownership.” (Ibid., 35) Something like that started to exist during the Axial Age in some of the main hubs of the Old World, while for large parts of humanity institutional facts in this sense did not yet exist.

In a similar manner, also Bhaskar’s Transformational Model of Social Activity (TMSA) refers to geo-historically specific elements. According to TMSA, society is both the ever present condition (material cause) and the continually reproduced outcome of human agency. People in their conscious activity unconsciously and sometimes consciously reproduce (and occasionally transform) the structures governing their substantive

activities of production. The purpose of social ontology and theory is to show that human activities can be reflexive and that actors can aim at emancipation from unwanted, unneeded and unnecessary sources of determination. The genesis of human actions lie in the reasons, intentions and plans of people. This model presupposes some particular and rather advanced properties of human agency (cf. Archer, 2000):

Human action is characterized by the striking phenomenon of intentionality. This seems to depend upon the feature that persons are material things with a degree of neurophysiological complexity which enables them not just, like the other higher-order animals, to initiate changes in a purposeful way, to monitor and control their performances, but to monitor the monitoring of these performances and to be capable of a commentary upon them. This capacity for second-order monitoring also makes possible a retrospective commentary upon actions, which gives a person's account of his or her own behaviour a special status, which is acknowledged in the best practice of all the psychological sciences. (Bhaskar, 1998, 38)

Compare this to the prevailing mentality in the ancient world that was in the process of reaching stage 7. We may recognise the ancient mentality as something familiar, but whether those societies really fulfil the criteria of Searlean or CR social ontologies is less evident. For example reflexivity, self-referential concepts, and second-order monitoring of activities may be more characteristic of 20th or 21st century world society than classical antiquity. For all the wisdom of Plato and Aristotle or Cicero and Lucretius – and similar figures in the Indus valley or China – most people in the ancient societies remained illiterate. For example, it is possible that Plato's hero Socrates could not read – at least he never wrote anything. What is more, Socrates seems to have exhibited features of bicameralism. He heard voices and was guided by them. Socrates's *daimon* was an external voice or command that would cause him to stop in his tracks. (For example Critchley, 2008, xvi) In his last days Socrates announced that “I am that gadfly which God has attached to the state”; and that “I am given to you by God” (Plato, 1999). As we know, Socrates was eventually indicted for failing to honour both Athenian democracy and its gods, and was condemned to death.

Literate ancient philosophers might have been less bicameral but nonetheless tended to reify social distinctions and institutions (to use concepts of critical social sciences). Archer (2010, 4) cites Plato's *Theaetetus* as the first ever characterisation of reflexivity, meaning “the conversation which the soul holds with herself in considering of anything”. However, Plato's or Aristotle's inner conversation does not mean a hypothetical attitude to the conventions or structures of society. For Aristotle “natural slaves”, women and lower-status men are essentially meant to serve the purpose of the good life of the aristocracy and free men. The outside world forms concentric circles of increasing barbarity. The further you go, the more barbarity you should expect to find. Like the apparent rotation of planets and stars – including the sun – around the Earth, this kind of ethnocentrism is essentially an illusion of perspective stemming from being familiar with things that are close; from social practices that are structured to serve the purpose of the few and their sense of community; and from asymmetrical relations of power. It is noteworthy that Aristotle did not support democracy even among free male citizens, but rather argued for a compromise between what he called polity and aristocracy (*aristoi* means literally ‘best persons’). For Aristotle, the true centre consists only of the central observer and of the few that are equal to him. In China, the Confucians reached similar conclusions regarding everyone's given, rightful place in society. The Confucians also entertained related ideas of governance by virtue and practical reason rather than by force, and of applying the principles of freedom and tolerance only to the

privileged few (for details and references, Patomäki, 2010, 184–8; for an explanation of why Aristotle’s theories did not allow him to look critically into his own conceptual metaphors and cognitive unconsciousness, see Lakoff and Johnson, 1999, 373–90).

Searlean and CR social ontologies focus on specific geo-historical formations from a rather limited perspective, largely ignoring their concrete historical emergence and development, diversity, and future possibilities. What Searle and critical realists describe is a literate and secularised world of humans with reflective consciousness and capacity for evaluating their own actions as well as social relations, rules, and principles (even when most of their everyday practices are based on unconscious rule-following). For one thing, this makes it difficult to study how reflective consciousness is dependent on earlier layers and how the earlier layers – and the analogues and metaphors constituting reflective consciousness – can be causally efficacious with regard to current actions, practices and institutions, while also being moulded by them. For example, at stage 7, bodily things such as breathe, blood, lungs, heart and head were turned into metaphors and started to denote psyche, spirit, soul, life, emotions, intelligence and self. The repertoire of simple affects that we share with other mammals was transformed into complex human emotions: fear became anxiety, shame was translated into guilt and mating was turned into sex. These and many other conscious emotions were made possible by analogues and metaphors, which have been subsequently used to debate and theorise justice, goodness, morality, emotions, and the meaning of human existence. Or to give another example, many of the features of the “bicameral world” remain efficacious in the 21st century globalised world. With the breakdown of the bicameral mind, the world of gods and their brain-induced voices receded and aspects of this “external” world were transformed into elements of the Background of social activities (to use Searle’s terminology; background capabilities have evolved through stages 1-7 and beyond). Yet in the 21st century many people continue to hear voices, religions are resurgent, and authoritarian leaders talking about god are widely followed. Religions can also be anti-authoritarian and secular ideologies may be functionally equivalent and structurally isomorphic with religions. Meanings change with context and new meanings emerge, yet their explanation may continue to require reference to earlier layers (these remarks do not imply the denial of relevance of fundamental existential and theological questions). Reflective consciousness and language are causally efficacious, but built on top of many layers. It is not only that the reflectively conscious self is context-dependent, but its potentially expanding powers are limited given the complexities of human constitution.

Social ontology should reflect the fact that human beings, social relations, and social wholes exist in diverse and evolving ways. Stage 7, or any stage beyond that, is merely a stage, not the end of history, and can be combined with other stages and developments. “It would be wrong to think that whatever the neurology of consciousness now may be, it is set for all time” (Jaynes, 2000, 125). The same holds true for forms of agency and such (metaphorical) concepts of social theory as “status functions”, “reproduction”, “structures”, “institutions”, or “positioning”. Their relevance is contingent and their meanings are shifting also in relation to the prevalence of different socio-historical formations. Our reflexivity and relationship to particular institutions such as money; our conceptions of self, space, and time; and the size and complexity of human organizations are all liable to change. Change and emergence take time, and certain categories may endure through a historical *longue durée*, but human/personal/social being is processual and historical and should be theorised as such.

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